

Comparison of direct energy deposition and powder bed fusion technology in the preparation of Ti–6Al–4V alloy

Daniela Medová^a, Anna Knaislová^a, Angelina Strakosova^{a,b,*}, Orsolya Molnárová^b, Jaroslav Čapek^b, Ilona Voňavková^a, Dalibor Vojtěch^a

^a Department of Metals and Corrosion Engineering, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague. Technická 5, 166 28, Prague, Czech Republic

^b Institute of Physics, Czech Academy of Sciences, Na Slovance 2, 182 00, Prague 8, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Handling editor: P Rios

Keywords:

Direct energy deposition
Powder bed fusion
Ti–6Al–4V alloy
Microstructure
Mechanical properties
Thermal stability

ABSTRACT

The Ti–6Al–4V alloy is the most widely used titanium-based alloy in aerospace and biomedical applications. Due to the complex shapes required for components in these application areas, additive manufacturing has become a promising option with its advantageous speed and precision. This study examined the impact of direct energy deposition (DED) and powder bed fusion (PBF) technologies on the resulting properties of the Ti–6Al–4V alloy. DED-produced samples showed almost fully dense structure, while PBF-produced ones were characterized by 0.3 % residual porosity. In all states, the α or α' phase predominated in the material microstructure. The Ti–6Al–4V alloy produced by different additive manufacturing methods showed comparable hardness values in both, as-printed (380 HV) and as-printed + heat-treated (370 HV) states. However, the samples printed by the PBF method exhibited higher tensile strength and yield strength than those printed by the DED method. These values before and after stress-relief heat treatment differed by approximately 100 MPa. Conversely, the DED-printed material is more stable at elevated temperatures (up to 800 °C) compared to the one printed by PBF.

1. Introduction

The Ti–6Al–4V alloy is the most widely used titanium alloy [1]. The alloy is used in automotive, aircraft, aerospace, chemical, and food industries [2]. Moreover, due to its suitable modulus of elasticity, high corrosion resistance, and high biocompatibility, the Ti–6Al–4V alloy is widely used in medical applications (dental, orthopaedic, and trauma implants) [3]. It is an $\alpha+\beta$ alloy, where aluminium (6 wt %) stabilizes the α phase and vanadium (4 wt %) stabilizes the β phase. In the microstructure of the Ti–6Al–4V alloy, the α phase predominates at ambient temperature and transforms into the β phase with increasing temperature [4]. The transition is completed at the β -transus temperature (approximately 980 °C) [5]. The β phase can decompose through diffusion or diffusionless processes. Diffusion processes are based on nucleation and grain growth, and the structure is then formed by primary β particles at the grain boundaries and Widmanstätten α lamellae. In diffusionless transformation, a martensitic α' structure is created [6]. It can be therefore said that a manufacturing process with its thermal history has a large impact on the microstructure and phase composition

of the Ti–6Al–4V alloy [7]. During the additive manufacturing (AM) of this alloy, predominantly needle-like martensite α' is expected to form within the β grains [8], whereas in wrought material, an α Widmanstätten structure forms in the β matrix [3]. Moreover, Lu et al. [9] found that a manufacturing process has an impact on the corrosion properties of the Ti–6Al–4V alloy when additively manufactured material exhibited better corrosion resistance and a more stable passivation film than the conventionally produced counterparts.

The Powder Bed Fusion (PBF) and the Direct Energy Deposition (DED) methods are the most common approaches for the AM of metallic materials [10]. PBF is a highly advanced technology that allows for rapid and precise building of objects using powders as input material [11]. Moreover, the possibility of the production of intricate and flexible structural designs has opened up new possibilities for the manufacture of lightweight materials with lattice structures that enable superior mechanical properties [12,13]. Other advantages include the diversity of input materials, environmental friendliness [14] and recyclability of powders [10]. The disadvantages of PBF technology include undesirable porosity and increased surface roughness [14], which negatively affects

* Corresponding author. Department of Metals and Corrosion Engineering, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague. Technická 5, 166 28, Prague, Czech Republic.

E-mail addresses: strakosn@vscht.cz, strakosova@fzu.cz (A. Strakosova).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2025.01.231>

Received 6 November 2024; Received in revised form 22 January 2025; Accepted 29 January 2025

Available online 1 February 2025

2238-7854/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

the microstructure and properties of materials. Similarly to other AM technologies, high thermal gradients occur during the PBF printing, which can lead to material cracking [15]. To prevent the formation of these defects, it is necessary to optimize AM parameters, such as powder layer thickness (or powder/wire feed rate in the case of the DED method), laser power, scanning speed, and hatching space [16].

The DED method is based on feeding raw material (powder or wire) directly into the deposition area, where it is immediately melted by a laser, electron beam or an electric arc, and the gradual movement of the deposition head creates individual layers [17,18]. The main advantage of the DED method lies in its ability to fabricate or repair large parts [19]. DED-produced materials typically exhibit lower surface roughness compared to objects produced by other additive manufacturing processes (e.g., SLM, EBM, etc.). The printing is not performed on a powder bed, thus avoiding the adhesion of unmelted powder to the surface [8]. Surface roughness is also influenced by surface oxidation [20] and the presence of open pores [8].

The investigation of the Ti–6Al–4V alloy produced by DED technology is at the beginning [21–24] compared to the alloy produced by the widely known PBF technology [25–33]. For example, Yang et al. [33] investigated morphology and substructure of α' martensite in the PBF-printed Ti–6Al–4V samples. The mechanical properties of the PBF-produced alloy were deeply studied in the work of Tong et al. [2]. The tensile behaviour of the Ti–6Al–4V printed by PBF was described in works [26,27]. The effect of heat treatment on the structure and properties of this type of alloy was studied in works [28,29,32,34]. On the contrary, current research on the Ti–6Al–4V alloy produced by DED is basic. The authors of the works [21,23,24] studied the development of microstructure and mechanical properties depending on printing conditions. Wu et al. [24] found that the size of columnar prior- β grains in DED-produced samples reaches lengths of 1–20 mm and widths in a range of 0.2–4 mm. According to Qian et al. [35], the lower and upper layers of DED material contain more martensitic phase than the middle layers. Oh et al. [22], and Kistler et al. [23] found that DED-printed Ti–6Al–4V alloy exhibits a defective microstructure with the lack-of-fusion as the main defect type.

Although research on DED-produced Ti–6Al–4V alloys is limited, there have been notable findings, such as the study by Malej [36] that explored the microstructure and mechanical properties of hybrid additive manufactured Ti–6Al–4V alloy, providing valuable insights into this less well-understood area. Despite the absence of many studies on DED-produced Ti–6Al–4V alloy, there are some interesting catches. Although the authors of the work [7] compared Ti–6Al–4V material properties derived from DED and PBF methods, they emphasized that more research is necessary to understand better the complex interrelationships between powder properties, processing conditions, additive manufacturing methods, microstructural transformations, and resultant mechanical properties. Moreover, research on additively manufactured Ti–6Al–4V alloy lacks knowledge about their thermal stability.

The aim of this work was the detailed investigation of the Ti–6Al–4V alloy produced by DED. Differences between Ti–6Al–4V alloy samples produced using DED and more common PBF technologies were also characterized. Samples were analysed in their as-printed and heat-treated states, focusing on microstructure and mechanical properties. Other objectives of this work entailed comparing the thermal stability of samples produced using DED and PBF technologies, utilizing hardness measurements as well as analyses of alpha lamellae width.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material and sample preparation

The material studied in this work is the Ti–6Al–4V alloy with a chemical composition corresponding to the ASTM F2924 standard (Table 1). The examined materials were produced using additive

Table 1

Chemical Composition of Ti–6Al–4V powder used for DED and PBF printing (according to the ASTM F2924 standard).

	Al	V	Ti
[wt. %]	5.5–6.5	3.5–4.5	bal.

manufacturing technologies: DED and PBF. For the samples produced using DED technology, the powder was manufactured by plasma atomization, while the powder for the PBF method was produced by gas atomization. The particle size distribution (PSD) of both powders was determined using the Malvern Panalytical analyzer.

The DED printing was conducted using the InssTek Mx-600 system (COMTES FHT a.s., Czech Republic) on the SDM800 module in the DMT printing mode. In this mode, the printer automatically adjusts the laser power to maintain consistent layer height. The printing strategy used was Spiral CFC + CF, which prints in a spiral starting from the centre. Odd-numbered layers follow a contour-fill-contour (CFC) pattern, with the infill printed clockwise. Even-numbered layers follow a contour-fill (CF) pattern, with the infill printed counterclockwise. Parameters of DED printing of Ti–6Al–4V alloy are shown in Table 2.

The studied material was printed in the shape of a cylinder approximately 5 cm high and 1 cm in diameter (see Fig. 1a). Transverse (cross-sectional) and longitudinal samples were taken from the bottom, middle, and upper parts of the studied material. Thus, a total of six samples were extracted from the original material as indicated by lines in Fig. 1a. Fig. 1b (red areas) shows the studied cross-sectional and longitudinal areas.

The chemical composition of the powder used for PBF printing is also provided in Table 1. The samples were printed on an M2 Cusing printer (Prospol spol. s r.o., Czech Republic) using a fiber laser with a power of 200 W and a chessboard scanning strategy [37]. The M2 Cusing printer uses an Nd:YAG laser, where the active material is an isotropic crystal of yttrium-aluminium garnet (YAG) doped with neodymium ions (Nd^{3+}). The parameters used for the PBF printing as listed in Table 3 are the result of optimization. These parameters are typically provided directly by the supplier of the material or adjusted by the manufacturer themselves. The alloy specimens had an overall length of 70 mm, while the 28 mm long test part (Fig. 2).

The studied DED-produced material was divided into samples corresponding to those produced by PBF using wire electrical discharge machining on the VUMA EID 5 M machine and precise metallographic cutting using an ATM Brillant 220 saw.

2.2. Heat treatment

Two types of heat treatment were performed on the Ti–6Al–4V alloy samples.

- Stress relief annealing – Conducted for 1.5 h at 820 °C under vacuum, with a furnace heating rate of 200 °C/h, followed by furnace cooling (recommended by the PBF printer manufacturer). This annealing was carried out in a vacuum annealing furnace Xerion.
- Annealing at temperatures ranging from 100 °C to 800 °C – Conducted for 2 h in air each on different samples, followed by rapid quenching in water. This annealing was aimed at determining the thermal stability of the material and was conducted in a Martinek MP 05–1.1 muffle furnace.

Table 2

Printing parameters of Ti–6Al–4V using DED technology.

Printing speed [mm/min]	Powder feed rate [g/min]	Shielding gas flow rate [l/min]	Build platform	Laser power [W]
850	1.0	21	CP Titan Grade 2	200–450

Fig. 1. Image of a sample produced by DED (a) and studied areas (b). (yellow arrow shows the printing direction).

Table 3
Basic printing parameters for PBF technology.

Laser power [W]	Scanning speed [mm/s]	Hatch distance [μm]	Layer thickness [μm]	Scanning strategy	Atmosphere
200	800	120	30	Chessboard	Ar

Fig. 2. Dimensions of PBF-printed samples for a tensile test. (arrow shows the printing direction; all dimensions are in mm).

2.3. Microstructure and phase composition

Study of the microstructure of Ti–6Al–4V alloys was conducted on metallographic cuts of individual representative samples. The samples were embedded in a VariDur 200 mounting resin and subsequently ground on a rotary grinder using SiC abrasive papers with increasing grit sizes (P240, P400, P800, P1200, P2500, and P4000). Polishing of the samples was initially carried out on Zeta synthetic cloth using diamond suspension in a water-based medium with a particle size of 3 μm , followed by diamond suspension with a particle size of 0.25 μm . Finally, a final polishing was performed on a neoprene cloth using a mixture of Eposil F suspension (colloidal silica, pH \approx 9.5, grain size 0.1 μm) and

hydrogen peroxide in a volume ratio of 8:2. After polishing, the samples were subjected to 5 min of ultrasonic treatment, rinsed with water and ethanol, and dried with warm air.

Porosity was evaluated using image analysis with the ImageJ computer software. The polished surfaces of the samples were captured using an optical microscope Zeiss Axio Observer D1m at 100 \times magnification. Values from individual images were averaged, and the corresponding 95% confidence interval was calculated. Samples for microstructure observation were etched using Kroll's reagent (100 ml H₂O, 6 ml HNO₃, and 3 ml HF), after being polished. Optical microscopy (OM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), stereomicroscopy, and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were used for structural examinations. OM Zeiss Axio Observer D1m, Nikon Eclipse MA200, stereomicroscope Olympus SZX10, SEM Tescan Mira equipped with an energy-dispersive detector (EDS, Oxford Instruments X-Max 20), and TEM FEI Tecnai TF20 X-twin were employed. For SEM imaging, samples were coated with a 5 nm gold layer using the Quorum Q150R ES instrument to enhance conductivity. Thin foils for TEM imaging were prepared using the focused ion beam (FIB) tool in SEM (FEI Quanta 3D FEG).

To investigate the influence of elevated temperatures on the microstructure of both DED and PBF-printed materials, the width of α lamellae was measured on the SEM images using ImageJ software. The measurement was performed on samples in the as-printed and in the as-printed + heat-treated (stress relief annealing) states and also after being exposed to elevated temperatures in the range of 100–800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. In each case, 20 lamellae were measured.

X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD) was used to identify phases presented in the Ti–6Al–4V material structure. XRD analysis was performed using a PANalytical X'Pert PRO instrument (Cu anode; generator settings - 30 mA, 40 kV; step size 0.0390; 2 θ angle range 5–90 $^{\circ}$).

2.4. Mechanical properties

Hardness measurements were conducted with a 1 kg load and a dwell time of 10 s using Struers Duramin 2 and Future-Tech FM-700 devices. To ensure sufficient statistics, 15 measurements were performed on each material. The average value and corresponding 95% confidence interval were calculated for each set of measurements.

The tensile test was conducted on “dog bone” shaped samples with

loading applied in a direction parallel to the build direction of the samples. For samples printed using DED technology, the “dog bone” shape was machined from a cylindrical rod. Samples printed using the PBF technology were directly printed into the corresponding “dog bone” shape. To eliminate potential biases caused by the production method, all “dog bone”-shaped samples were ground on all sides using P1200 SiC abrasive paper to ensure uniformity in the tested surfaces before mechanical property measurements. Tensile tests were performed on an Instron 5882 device. Three measurements were performed for each state of the Ti–6Al–4V alloy at room temperature with a strain rate of 0.001 s^{-1} . Subsequently, the fracture surfaces were analysed using SEM Tescan Mira.

3. Results

3.1. Microstructure and phase composition

First, the starting powders were examined. Particle size distribution histograms are shown in Fig. 3. It is evident that the powder used for the DED method (Fig. 3a) is characterized by a larger diameter compared to the PBF powder (Fig. 3b). According to the results of PSD measurements, the DED particle size ranged from 49.9 to 134 μm , with an average particle size of 82 μm , while the PBF powder size ranged from 21.6 to 47.8 μm , with an average particle size of 32.2 μm .

The morphology and microstructure of the Ti–6Al–4V powders are shown in Fig. 4. In Fig. 4a,c, it is evident that both powders are characterized by a variety of particle sizes, which is consistent with the results shown in Fig. 3. Overall, the particles are spherical in shape. Small satellite particles attached to the large ones are also visible in Fig. 4a,c. In the microstructure of the powders (Fig. 4b,d), martensitic phase α' needles can be seen, likely formed due to the high cooling rate during the plasma or gas atomization process. Irregularly shaped pores are also visible (see yellow arrow in Fig. 4b,d).

The planar porosity was measured on the DED-printed samples in transverse and longitudinal directions in the lower, middle, and upper regions relative to the build direction of the samples. As observed in Fig. 5a, sparsely occurring uniformly distributed spherical pores (dark

spots) are visible on the samples. Given the shape and size of these defects, it can be concluded that they are gas pores [8]. Porosity was evaluated using the ImageJ program from these (Fig. 5) and similar images.

The results of the porosity measurements of the studied material are summarized in Table 4. As shown in Table 4, all the examined samples exhibited very low porosity values, indicating nearly 100% density of the compact product. On the other hand, the relative density of the PBF-produced samples was measured only on the middle part of the sample in the printing direction and is equal to $99.7 \pm 0.1 \%$.

A more detailed study of the microstructure was conducted again on transverse and longitudinal sections of the samples printed using DED technology in both the as-printed state and the printed + heat-treated state (stress relief annealing). When examining samples printed using PBF technology, samples in the same states (as-printed and printed + annealed) were observed in the longitudinal section. Samples from the middle of the material printed using DED were investigated using a stereomicroscope at $10 \times$ magnification in both transverse and longitudinal sections (Fig. 6). In Fig. 6, the boundaries of the melt pools, which follow the movement of the laser and indicate the printing strategy, can be seen. In the transverse section (Fig. 6a), equiaxed grains are visible, while in the longitudinal section (Fig. 6b), characteristic elongated grains in the printing direction are observed. The same grain shapes were observed in the works of Wu et al. [24] and Liu et al. [8].

Fig. 7 shows longitudinal sections in the middle part of the Ti–6Al–4V alloy produced by DED technology in both printed and annealed states.

In the structure of the samples printed using DED technology, melt pools following the movement of the laser beam are visible (Fig. 7a and b, indicated by No. 1). Also visible are prior- β grains growing toward the heat source during solidification through several layers. The columnar prior- β grains are thus elongated in the building direction because the grains in the previous layer act as nucleation sites for newly formed grains in the newly deposited layer [38]. The prior- β grains, formed during the rapid solidification of the alloy during DED printing, exhibited a wide range of sizes, with measured widths ranging from tens of μm up to 1 mm and lengths from hundreds of μm to several mm.

Fig. 3. PSD of Ti–6Al–4V powder used for the DED (a) and PBF (b) methods.

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of Ti-6Al-4V powder used for DED (a, b) and PBF (c, d) methods: powder morphology (a, c) and cross-section microstructure (b, d). (yellow arrows show pores).

Fig. 5. Representative OM images in the volume of DED-printed Ti-6Al-4V alloy in the longitudinal (a) and transverse (b) directions.

Table 4
Planar porosity of Ti-6Al-4V samples printed using DED technology in the lower part, middle part, upper part, and in longitudinal and transverse sections.

Observed area		Porosity [%]
Lower part	Longitudinal cut	0.020 ± 0.010
	Transverse cut	0.014 ± 0.002
Middle part	Longitudinal cut	0.004 ± 0.001
	Transverse cut	0.020 ± 0.005
Upper part	Longitudinal cut	0.025 ± 0.010
	Transverse cut	0.005 ± 0.001
Average porosity		0.014 ± 0.006

According to Ref. [36], the α phase occurs at the boundaries of the prior- β grains (indicated by No. 2 in Fig. 7). The width of the as-printed and as-printed + heat-treated martensite laths was measured to be $0.65 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.89 \pm 0.12 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. According to A. Azarniya et al. [3], needle-like martensitic α' and lamellar Widmanstätten α phase with β phase between them can be found inside the prior- β grains [3]. In the middle part of the DED-printed sample, an $\alpha + \beta$ microstructure is present, as observed in the detailed SEM image (Fig. 7e). The $\alpha + \beta$ microstructure (see Fig. 7c) contains lamellar α phase bordered by rod-like β phase [34]. As shown in Fig. 7f, annealing contributed to the thickening of the α lamellae in the $\alpha + \beta$ microstructure, which can lead to a decrease in yield strength (YS) but an improvement in material

Fig. 6. Stereomicroscope images of the microstructure of the DED-printed Ti-6Al-4V alloy in the transverse (a) and longitudinal (b) directions. (arrow shows the printing direction).

Fig. 7. OM (a–d) and SEM (e, f) micrographs of the middle part of DED-printed Ti-6Al-4V alloy in the printed state (a, c, e) and printed + heat-treated (820 °C/1.5 h, vacuum, furnace cooling) (b, d, f) state. (yellow arrows show the printing direction; 1 – melting pool boundaries, 2 – prior-β grain boundaries, 3 – pores, 4 – α phase lamellae, 5 – β phase).

ductility [20]. Annealing also led to the coarsening of the β phase. In Fig. 7f, the formation of fine β particles within the α lamellae can be observed. The same α + β structure was also observed in other studies [3,

20]. Fig. 8 shows longitudinal sections of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy produced by PBF technology in both as-printed and as-printed + annealed states.

Fig. 8. OM (a–d) and SEM (e, f) micrographs of the PBF-printed Ti-6Al-4V alloy microstructure in the printed state (a, c, e), printed + heat-treated (820 °C/1.5 h, vacuum, furnace cooling) (b, d, f) states. (yellow arrows show the printing direction; 1 – grain boundaries, 2 – pores, 3 – martensitic needles, 4 – α phase lamellae, 5 – β phase).

In the samples produced using PBF technology, columnar prior- β grains are again visible in both the printed and printed + annealed states (see Fig. 8a and b). According to Malej et al. [36], the prior- β grains in the PBF-printed sample are smaller than those in the DED-printed sample, which can also be observed in Figs. 7 and 8. The prior- β grains, formed during the rapid solidification of the alloy during PBF printing, exhibited a wide range of sizes, with the measured widths ranging from tens to several hundred μm and lengths from hundreds of μm to one mm. In the PBF-printed state, the prior- β grains are filled with fine martensitic α' needles growing from the grain boundaries (indicated by No. 1 and No. 3 in Fig. 8) [39]. The width of the martensite laths in the PBF as-produced and as-produced + heat-treated samples are equal to $0.68 \pm 0.14 \mu\text{m}$ and $1.19 \pm 0.19 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. This martensite structure is metastable, and therefore during annealing, the α' needles transform into the α phase, which is a stable structure. Since the annealing process lasted 1.5 h and cooling occurred slowly, vanadium had enough time to migrate towards the edges of the martensitic needles, subsequently promoting β phase formation. As a result, a two-phase structure of prevailing thin α lamellae separated by rod-like β phase is formed (Fig. 8f). Fig. 8f also shows the coarsening of the microstructure of the PBF-printed Ti-6Al-4V alloy after stress relief annealing. The effect of heat treatment on the microstructure of the PBF-printed Ti-6Al-4V alloy was studied by Etesami et al. [34], who also observed a martensitic α' structure in the printed state that gradually decomposes

to form an $\alpha + \beta$ structure.

Detailed microstructure characterization in the middle part of both DED-printed and DED-printed + heat-treated (820 °C/1.5 h, vacuum, furnace cooling) materials was investigated using TEM analysis. TEM micrographs of thin foils prepared using FIB are shown in Fig. 9. It can be seen that stress relief annealing caused changes in the additively manufactured Ti-6Al-4V alloy microstructure. More precisely, it caused the microstructure coarsening. It can be seen (Fig. 9, yellow arrows) that α lamellae increased in size due to stress-relief annealing.

A detailed TEM micrograph of the DED-printed Ti-6Al-4V alloy is shown in Fig. 10a. One can see several hundreds of nm wide α lamellae. Fig. 10b shows the selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern of the selected area (red circle in Fig. 10a). Due to the small size of the β phase located between two α lamellae, the nanodiffraction pattern contains reflections of both alpha and beta phases (Fig. 10b).

Heat treatment, precisely stress-relief annealing at 820 °C for 1.5h in a vacuum, caused a coarsening of the microstructure, which has been already observed in Fig. 9. A detailed TEM micrograph of the DED-printed + heat-treated material is shown in Fig. 11. It can be seen that the stress relief annealing has caused the coarsening of both α and β phases that were identified in zonal axes $[-111]$ and $[113]$, respectively (Fig. 11b and c).

The phase composition of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy was examined using XRD analysis. For comparison, measurements were taken not only of the

Fig. 9. TEM images of the DED-printed (a), the DED-printed + heat-treated (b) Ti-6Al-4V alloy. (yellow arrows show the α phase, blue arrows show the β phase).

Fig. 10. TEM micrograph (a) and SAED pattern (b) of the DED-printed Ti-6Al-4V. (red circle indicates SAED area).

Fig. 11. TEM micrograph (a) and SAED patterns (b, c) of the DED-printed Ti-6Al-4V. (yellow square indicates the SAED area for α -Ti and blue square – for β -Ti).

samples printed using DED and PBF technologies but also of a sample produced by forging and the powder used in DED printing. From the material printed using DED technology, two samples were taken for XRD analysis, one from the upper part and one from the lower part. The results of the analysis are summarized in Fig. 12, where the corresponding positions of the standards are indicated.

The semi-quantitative contents of the phases present in the Ti-6Al-4V alloy are summarized in Table 5. It is evident (Fig. 12 and Table 5) that when the sample is printed by DED, the microstructure predominantly contains the α phase. When using the PBF technology for

material printing, XRD confirmed the presence of the α' phase in the form of martensite. The α and martensitic α' phases have similar diffraction lines, making them difficult to distinguish.

The martensitic α' phase in the PBF printed material was also confirmed by the microstructure study (Fig. 8). Comparing the sample taken from the upper and lower parts of the DED printed sample, the lower sample shows almost 100% α' phase. It is likely the martensitic α' phase (Fig. 13), which probably formed due to faster cooling of the lower part of the sample, as the heat dissipates into the cold substrate [3]. In the upper part, the β phase is additionally detected, probably

Fig. 12. XRD patterns of the phase composition of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy depending on the manufacturing method. (HT – heat-treated by stress relief annealing).

Table 5

Semi-quantitative proportions of α and β phases in the Ti-6Al-4V alloy depending on the manufacturing method (according to XRD analysis).

Phase	DED Powder	DED Lower Part	DED Upper Part	DED + HT	PBF	PBF + HT	Forged
Semi-quantitative proportions [%]							
α/α'	100	100	98	100	100	99	96
β	–	Traces	2	Traces	–	1	4

indicating an $\alpha + \beta$ structure of the material, like the middle part of the material which can be observed in SEM and TEM images (Figs. 7 and 10).

3.2. Mechanical properties

Measurement of hardness (HV1) of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy

manufactured by DED technology depending on the position in the studied sample is summarized in Table 6.

In Table 6, a slightly higher hardness can be observed in the DED printed material sample taken from the bottom part of the studied material compared to samples taken from the middle and upper parts. This increased hardness is attributed to the harder martensitic α' phase, visible in the accompanying Fig. 13. According to the measured data, no anisotropy in properties is observed between the transverse and longitudinal sections.

Table 7 summarizes the results of hardness measurements of Ti-6Al-4V alloy depending on the manufacturing method and heat treatment (stress relief annealing). It can be seen (Table 7) that after stress relief annealing, there was a slight decrease in hardness values of both DED and PBF-printed samples compared to the as-printed state. According to Lekoadi et al. [40], this decrease was likely caused by microstructure coarsening and an increase in the β phase content, which can be observed in Fig. 8. Moreover, the decrease is also caused by the

Fig. 13. SEM micrographs of the lower part of the DED-printed Ti-6Al-4V sample in the transverse (a) and longitudinal (b) cuts. (yellow arrow shows the printing direction).

Table 6

Hardness in various regions of the studied material manufactured by DED in the as-printed state.

Observed area		Hardness HV1
Lower part	Longitudinal cut	411 ± 5
	Transverse cut	398 ± 3
Middle part	Longitudinal cut	382 ± 3
	Transverse cut	388 ± 2
Upper part	Longitudinal cut	383 ± 3
	Transverse cut	374 ± 2

Table 7

Overview of hardness values of samples manufactured using DED and PBF technologies in as-printed and as-printed + annealed (stress relief) states in longitudinal sections.

		HV1
DED	as-printed state	382 ± 3
	Annealed state	372 ± 3
PBF	as-printed state	380 ± 5
	Annealed state	370 ± 3

transformation from α' martensite to microstructure consisting of $\alpha + \beta$ phases.

Uniaxial tensile tests were conducted on samples printed using DED and PBF technologies in the as-printed and as-printed + heat-treated (stress relief annealing) states. The individual stress-strain curves of the samples are shown in Fig. 14. It can be seen that the DED-printed material (Fig. 14, green lines) is characterized by lower values of yield strength (YS), ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and elongation (A) compared to the PBF-produced one (Fig. 14, yellow lines). This applies to both as-produced and heat-treated states.

Table 8 shows higher values of UTS and YS and lower values of A for samples printed using the PBF technology compared to when DED printing is used. These values are likely again attributed to the finer martensitic microstructure (see Fig. 8) where the prior- β grains are several times smaller compared to those obtained in the counterparts produced by DED (Fig. 7). The martensitic structure present in PBF-printed samples is stronger compared to the $\alpha + \beta$ structure of the DED-printed sample due to dislocation strengthening and high lattice strain [30].

SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces of samples printed using DED and PBF methods are presented in Fig. 15. On the macrograph of the fracture surface of the DED-printed sample (Fig. 15a), small pores and microcracks are visible (marked as No. 1, 2). At higher magnification, a ductile fracture surface with a typical dimple morphology was observed (Fig. 15b). Microcracks were also observed (Fig. 15b, marked as No. 3). Fractography of the PBF-printed sample revealed a higher occurrence of

Fig. 14. Representative stress-true strain curves of the additively manufactured Ti-6Al-4V alloy.

Table 8

Values of yield strength (YS), ultimate tensile strength (UTS), and elongation (A) of Ti-6Al-4V alloy fabricated using DED and PBF technologies in the as-printed state.

Sample	YS [MPa]	UTS [MPa]	A [%]
DED (as-printed)	1069 ± 96	1126 ± 55	6.1 ± 2.7
DED (as-printed + annealed)	942 ± 38	1026 ± 25	6.4 ± 1.6
PBF (as-printed)	1170 ± 19	1316 ± 12	2.9 ± 1.2
PBF (as-printed + annealed)	1052 ± 7	1230 ± 23	10.3 ± 1.1

pores (Fig. 15c, marked as No. 1). However, ductile fracture was observed on most of the fracture surface (Fig. 15d).

SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces of additively manufactured samples after being heat-treated (stress relief annealing) were also investigated. Dimple morphology, which is typical for ductile fracture, was observed on the fracture surfaces of both examined samples (Fig. 16).

3.3. Thermal stability

The thermal stability of the materials was monitored through hardness measurements. The results for individual samples were plotted in graphs, with 95% confidence intervals used as error bars. The plots (see Fig. 17) show the comparison of HV1 for samples manufactured using different technologies in as-printed and heat-treated (stress relief annealing) states.

For the material printed using DED technology in the as-printed state (see Fig. 17, upper line), almost no changes in hardness values were observed within the temperature range from 100 °C to 600 °C. A slight decrease in hardness is observed between 600 °C and 800 °C, likely due to mild grain coarsening. The material produced by the DED method + heat-treated (stress relief annealing) shows as more stable at temperatures up to 800 °C.

In Fig. 17 (bottom line), an increase in hardness is observed for the alloy manufactured via PBF in the as-printed state within the temperature range of 100 °C–500 °C. Upon exceeding the annealing temperature of 500 °C, there is a decrease in material hardness. For the alloy manufactured via PBF in the annealed state, there was almost no increase in hardness observed at 500 °C, unlike the as-printed sample (Fig. 17, bottom line). The stable behaviour in the range of 100–800 °C is likely again due to the absence of a martensitic structure in the annealed PBF sample, similar to the DED-manufactured sample, which also features an $\alpha + \beta$ structure in its initial state (Fig. 8f). Therefore, there is no martensitic decomposition under elevated annealing temperatures.

The determination of the influence of elevated temperatures during thermal stability examination was also monitored through α lamellae width measurements. The results for individual samples (before exposure to elevated temperatures and after exposure to 500 and 800 °C) were plotted in graphs with 95% confidence intervals used as error bars. Fig. 18 shows the comparison of α lamellae width for samples manufactured using different additive manufacturing technologies in their as-printed and as-printed + annealed states. It can be seen (Fig. 18) that the α lamellae width remains almost the same size after being annealed at a temperature of 500 °C in all materials. Annealing at 800 °C caused only a slight increase in the α lamellae size except for the DED-printed + annealed material where the size remains unchanged.

SEM micrographs used to measure the α lamellae widths are shown in Figs. 19 and 20. The microstructures of the material produced by DED and PBF in their as-printed state after being exposed to 800 °C are shown in Fig. 19. The α phase lamellae became coarser compared to the additive manufactured Ti-6Al-4V alloys in their as-built states (Fig. 7e and 8e). It can also be seen (Fig. 19b) that the β phase was formed at the boundaries of α lamellae due to exposure to 800 °C for 2 h in the case of PBF-produced material.

Microstructure changes of the as-printed + heat-treated samples as a

Fig. 15. SEM micrographs (a, c) and detailed SEM micrographs (b, d) of the fracture surfaces of the DED (a, b) and PBF-printed (c, d) Ti-6Al-4V alloy.

result of exposure to 800 °C are shown in Fig. 20. The microstructures depicted in Fig. 20 are very similar to those $\alpha + \beta$ structures depicted in Fig. 19, but a bit coarser. It can also be seen (Fig. 20b) that the least impact on the microstructure coarsening of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy is observed when the material is produced by the PBF method and consequently heat-treated by stress relief annealing at 820 °C for 1.5 h (Fig. 8f).

4. Discussion

4.1. Microstructure and phase composition

The default powders used for both DED and PBF manufacturing methods meet the requirements (such as particle size and morphology) for a good additive manufacturing process [20]. For example, powders' regular and spherical shape allows for better packing density (PBF) and consistent flow (DED) of powders. Also, the average powder size was measured to be 82 μm for DED and 32.2 μm for the PBF method, while the recommended sizes ranged between 20 and 40 μm for the PBF process in contrast with 45–150 μm for the DED process [20]. Both powders are characterized by a fine martensite microstructure (Figs. 7 and 8), which is the result of rapid solidification during the production method [41].

When comparing the impact of DED and PBF technologies on the resulting microstructure (Fig. 12, Table 5), the $\alpha + \beta$ microstructure predominates in the as-produced state of the DED-printed samples, which was mainly observed in the middle and upper part of the printed material. Only the lower part contains a significant fraction of α' martensite due to the highest cooling rate. This is different from the situation where the PBF method is used for printing, where the α'

martensitic structure is present in the printed state and the $\alpha + \beta$ microstructure is observed only after annealing. The PBF-printed samples exhibited several times finer prior- β grains compared to their DED-printed counterparts, while their martensite lath widths were comparable (Fig. 18). These differences are due to the slower cooling rate during the DED printing process in which the built part is not surrounded by thermally conductive alloy powder [8]. On the other hand, the forged material shows the presence of both α and β phases. This is attributed to the higher cooling rates of additive manufacturing [8] compared to traditional manufacturing methods. In contrast, the forged sample also shows the presence of the β phase, consistent with literature findings [42,43].

The diffraction lines (Fig. 12) of the α and martensitic α' phases are very similar, making them difficult to distinguish. The presence of the martensitic α' phase in the PBF printed material was further validated by the microstructure study. Wysocki et al. [42] found no β phase in the PBF printed sample via XRD analysis, while Panin et al. [26] reported that the β phase did not exceed 2 vol% in PBF materials. Post-annealing of the PBF printed sample resulted in a slight decrease in the α phase as the martensitic α' phase transformed into an $\alpha + \beta$ structure. When comparing samples from the upper and lower parts of the DED printed material, the lower sample showed nearly 100% α phase, likely indicating the martensitic α' phase. This is probably due to the faster cooling rate at the lower part of the sample, where heat dissipates into the cold substrate [3]. In the upper part, the β phase was also detected, suggesting an $\alpha + \beta$ structure, which is supported by SEM images. Zhang et al. [44] similarly observed an $\alpha + \beta$ structure in DED printed samples in their research. The presence of both α and β phases was confirmed by TEM analysis in the DED-printed and DED-printed + heat-treated materials (Figs. 9–11). A coarser α lamellae structure with a conspicuous

Fig. 16. SEM micrographs (a, c) and detailed SEM micrographs (b, d) of the fracture surfaces of the DED (a, b) and PBF-printed (c, d) Ti-6Al-4V alloy after being heat-treated (820 °C/1.5 h, vacuum, furnace cooling).

presence of the β phase of the heat-treated Ti-6Al-4V alloy (Fig. 11) was observed compared to the as-printed one (Fig. 10). The same finding was described in Ref. [25], where the Ti-6Al-4V alloy was produced by the SLM method.

The results of porosity measurements suggest the isotropic behaviour of the material (Table 4). Therefore, it can be asserted that this is a high-quality product with a minimal amount of manufacturing defects and is thus expected to have good mechanical properties. Kistler et al. [23] investigated the effect of printing conditions on the porosity of Ti-6Al-4V alloy samples printed using the DED technology. All their samples exhibited low porosity (less than 0.3%), which is higher than the values measured in our work. Lack of fusion (LOF) defects with a length of 200–300 μm as well as pores and unmelted powders were found in the DED-printed Ti-6Al-4V material structure by Oh et al. [22]. Sahoo et al. [45] achieved porosity in the DED-printed Ti-6Al-4V sample of approximately 0.01% due to optimized conditions, a value almost identical to the results of this work. Wu et al. [31] examined the porosity of the same alloy but printed using PBF technology. They found porosity ranging from 0.0027% to 0.0617%, which is about half of the value observed by us. According to Cao et al. [46], the porosity in PBF-printed Ti-6Al-4V material ranges from 0.23% to 0.7%. Similar values ($0.49 \pm 0.17\%$) were observed in the work of Roudnická [47]. These values were significantly higher than the porosity observed in this work for the DED-printed material. Moreover, no LOF or unmelted particles were observed in our work.

4.2. Mechanical properties

The DED-printed material sample from the bottom part of the studied material shows higher hardness compared to samples from the middle and upper parts (Table 6). This increase in hardness is attributed to the presence of the harder martensitic α' phase. The formation of this martensitic phase is likely due to higher cooling rates and heat dissipation into the cold substrate. The measured data indicates no anisotropy in properties between the transverse and longitudinal sections.

Stress relief annealing led to a slight decrease in the hardness of DED-printed samples compared to their as-printed state (Table 7). PBF-printed samples also exhibited a decrease in hardness post-annealing. According to Lekoadi et al. [40], this decrease is likely due to microstructure coarsening and an increase in the β phase, which was also observed in our work. Fig. 18 shows that stress relief annealing caused the martensite lamellae coarsening of both the DED and PBF-produced materials. Softening due to the coarsening of microstructure is reflected by the Hall-Petch equation, where K_1 and K_2 are material-specific constants, d represents grain size, and HV denotes Vickers hardness [48].

$$HV = K_1 + K_2 \cdot d^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

Uniaxial tensile tests were performed on samples printed with DED and PBF technologies in the as-printed and as-printed + heat-treated conditions (Fig. 14 and Table 8). The higher UTS and YS values for the PBF-printed samples compared to the DED-printed ones, are likely due

Fig. 17. Change in microhardness (HV1) of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy as a result of different temperatures (from 100 to 800 °C) with a holding time of 2h (samples were water-cooled).

Fig. 18. Alpha lamellae widths depending on temperature with a holding time of 2h (samples were water-cooled).

Fig. 19. SEM micrographs of the microstructure of DED (a) and PBF (b) printed Ti-6Al-4V as a result of annealing at 800 °C for 2h (samples were water-cooled). (1 – α phase lamellae, 2 – β phase).

Fig. 20. SEM micrographs of the microstructure of DED (a) and PBF (b) printed and heat-treated (820 °C/1.5 h, vacuum, furnace cooling) Ti-6Al-4V alloy as a result of annealing at 800 °C for 2h (samples were water-cooled).

to the presence of finer prior- β grains that have a greater impact on the tensile properties than on the microhardness. On the other hand, the lower values of A for the Ti-6Al-4V produced by PBF compared to those produced by DED can be attributed to the more defective microstructure, as can be seen from Fig. 15a,c. The martensitic structure in PBF-printed samples is stronger than the $\alpha + \beta$ structure because of dislocation strengthening and high lattice strain [47]. Yu et al. [49] measured comparable values of YS (976 ± 24 MPa), UTS (1099 ± 2 MPa), and A (4.9 ± 0.1 %) for samples printed using DED technology, similar to our findings. Similar values were also reported by Carroll et al. [50], with a YS of 960 ± 26 MPa, UTS of 1063 ± 20 MPa, but they observed significantly higher values of A (13.3 ± 1.8 %). The mechanical properties of PBF-printed Ti-6Al-4V alloy were studied by Tao et al. [27], who measured a YS of approximately 1180 MPa and UTS of approximately 1310 MPa, closely matching our measured values. In contrast, Qian et al. [35] reported lower values of YS and UTS and A of approximately 5 %.

The stress relief annealing at 820 °C for 1.5 h caused a drop in the YS and UTS values but naturally increased the A values for both DED and PBF-printed Ti-6Al-4V materials (see Fig. 14, Table 8). However, although the material produced by PBF remained porous after heat treatment (Fig. 16c), the alloy was characterized by higher mechanical properties compared to the DED-produced one. The decrease of tensile properties can be explained by the complete decomposition of the α' martensite to the α and β phases that caused the drop of YS and UTS but an increase of elongation of the Ti-6Al-4V material. According to

Ref. [29], this decomposition takes place at temperatures higher than 800 °C. These changes in mechanical properties can also be explained by the coarsening of the alpha lamellae widths (Fig. 18), which was higher in the PBF-produced material (from 0.68 ± 0.14 μm and 1.19 ± 0.19 μm) compared to the DED-produced one (from 0.65 ± 0.05 μm and 0.89 ± 0.12 μm).

4.3. Thermal stability

It can be seen (Table 7 and Fig. 17) that DED and PBF-produced materials are characterized by similar hardness in the as-printed and as-printed + heat-treated states. However, these alloys have different responses to elevated temperatures (Fig. 17). For the material produced using DED technology in its as-printed and as-printed + heat-treated states, the hardness values remained almost unchanged within the temperature range of 100–600 °C and 100–800 °C, respectively (Fig. 17, upper line). Between 600 °C and 800 °C, a slight reduction in hardness was noted, probably due to mild microstructure coarsening. The alloy produced via PBF in the as-printed state shows an increase in hardness within the temperature range of 100 °C–500 °C (Fig. 17, bottom line). This increase can likely be attributed to the gradual decomposition of the martensitic α' phase and the refinement of the microstructure through the formation of a fine β phase [51]. Once the annealing temperature exceeds 500 °C, there is a decrease in hardness, which, according to studies [32,51], may be due to the breakdown of the martensitic phase into a mixture of $\alpha + \beta$. This leads to an increase and

coarsening of the β phase as well as the release of internal stress.

When comparing the thermal stability of materials printed using DED and PBF technologies (Fig. 17), the material printed with DED technology appears more stable up to 800 °C. This stability is likely because the DED-printed material maintains an $\alpha + \beta$ structure in the as-printed state, which remains stable up to 800 °C. In contrast, the material printed with PBF technology exhibits material hardening at 500 °C and subsequent softening. Unlike the DED-printed material, the PBF-printed material in the as-printed state shows a martensitic α' structure, which, according to studies [51,52], decomposes and refines, leading to temporary hardening at 500 °C.

Microstructure changes depending on chosen elevated temperatures (500 and 800 °C) were examined through lamellae width measurements. It was found that the microstructure of all materials remained unchanged when it was exposed to the temperature of 500 °C (see Fig. 18). Temperature of 800 °C caused only a slight increase in the lamellae width, which is also shown in Figs. 19 and 20, because the chosen temperature was lower than the β -transus one. Similar results were obtained by Refs. [28,29,53] describing the influence of different heat treatment modes on the microstructure changes of the conventionally produced and PBF additively manufactured Ti-6Al-4V alloy, respectively.

5. Conclusions

In this study, the properties of Ti-6Al-4V alloy printed using two technologies - Direct Energy Deposition (DED) and Powder Bed Fusion (PBF) - were compared. The materials were examined in both as-printed and as-printed + stress-relief annealed states (820 °C/1.5 h, vacuum, furnace cooling). Microstructure, mechanical properties of samples, and thermal stability were investigated.

The quality of DED-printed material was verified by measuring areal porosity, confirming compact, nearly pore-free material suitable for both structural and medical applications. XRD analysis of Ti-6Al-4V alloy manufactured by DED and PBF technologies revealed predominantly α (α') phase within columnar prior- β grains in all states. DED fabrication resulted in α lamellae formation predominantly inside prior- β grains with a small fraction of β phase. In contrast, PBF printing led to the formation of the martensitic α' phase.

Hardness in the as-printed states of DED and PBF samples was comparable. DED-printed samples exhibited a hardness of HV1 = 382 ± 3, whereas PBF samples showed HV1 = 380 ± 5, slightly higher than literature values, likely due to different printing parameters.

Samples printed by DED showed lower yield strength (YS), ultimate tensile strength (UTS), and higher elongation (A) compared to those printed by PBF. The increased values in PBF-printed samples were attributed to the martensitic structure absent in DED-printed samples. Fractography of fracture surfaces in all states of additively manufactured Ti-6Al-4V alloy predominantly revealed ductile morphology.

Regarding thermal stability assessed by Vickers hardness measurements, the material printed by DED appeared more stable in the temperature range of 100 °C–800 °C compared to PBF-printed material (in both as-printed and as-printed + heat-treated states). In contrast, PBF-printed material in the as-printed state exhibited significant hardening, with peak hardness observed at 500 °C/2 h (HV1 = 432 ± 3), likely due to gradual refinement of martensitic structure, a phenomenon not observed in DED-printed material.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Daniela Medová: Investigation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Anna Knaislová:** Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Angelina Strakosova:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Orsolya Molnáróvá:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Jaroslav Čapek:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing.

Ilna Voňavková: Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Dalibor Vojtěch:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing.

Data availability

The data used in this manuscript are available in the Zenodo repository at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13908585>.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

This publication was supported by the project “Mechanical Engineering of Biological and Bio-inspired Systems”, funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research. It was also supported from the grant of Specific university research–grant No A1_FCHT_2024_007. We acknowledge CzechNanoLab Research Infrastructure supported by MEYS CR (LM2023051).

References

- [1] Arrazola PJ, Garay A, Iriarte LM, Armendia M, Marya S, Le Maître F. Machinability of titanium alloys (Ti6Al4V and Ti555.3). *J Mater Process Technol* 2009;209(5): 2223–30.
- [2] Tong J, Bowen CR, Persson J, Plummer A. Mechanical properties of titanium-based Ti-6Al-4V alloys manufactured by powder bed additive manufacture 2017;33(2): 138–48.
- [3] Azarniya A, Colera XG, Mirzaali MJ, Sovizi S, Bartolomeu F, St Węglowski Mk, Wits WW, Yap CY, Ahn J, Miranda G, Silva FS, Madaah Hosseini HR, Ramakrishna S, Zadpoor AA. Additive manufacturing of Ti-6Al-4V parts through laser metal deposition (LMD): process, microstructure, and mechanical properties. *J Alloys Compd* 2019;804:163–91.
- [4] Philip JT, Mathew J, Kuriachen B. Tribology of Ti6Al4V: a review. *Friction* 2019;7(6):497–536.
- [5] Antolak-Dudka A, Czujko T, Durejko T, Stepniowski WJ, Ziętała M, Łukasiewicz J. Comparison of the microstructural, mechanical and corrosion resistance properties of Ti6Al4V samples manufactured by LENS and subjected to various heat treatments. *Materials* 2024;17(5):1166.
- [6] Gil FJ, Ginebra MP, Manero JM, Planell JA. Formation of α -Widmanstätten structure: effects of grain size and cooling rate on the Widmanstätten morphologies and on the mechanical properties in Ti6Al4V alloy. *J Alloys Compd* 2001;329(1): 142–52.
- [7] Ma HY, Wang JC, Qin P, Liu YJ, Chen LY, Wang LQ, Zhang LC. Advances in additively manufactured titanium alloys by powder bed fusion and directed energy deposition: microstructure, defects, and mechanical behavior. *J Mater Sci Technol* 2024;183:32–62.
- [8] Liu S, Shin YC. Additive manufacturing of Ti6Al4V alloy: a review. *Mater Des* 2019; 164:107552.
- [9] Lu WQ, Liu YJ, Wu X, Liu XC, Wang JC. Corrosion and passivation behavior of Ti-6Al-4V surfaces treated with high-energy pulsed laser: a comparative study of cast and 3D-printed specimens in a NaCl solution. *Surf Coating Technol* 2023;470: 129849.
- [10] Srivastava AK, Kumar A, Kumar P, Gautam P, Dogra N. Research progress in metal additive manufacturing: challenges and Opportunities. *Int J Interact Des Manuf* 2023.
- [11] Yao L, Ramesh A, Xiao Z, Chen Y, Zhuang Q. Multimetal research in powder bed fusion: a review. *Materials* 2023;16(12):4287.
- [12] Wu Z-Y, Liu Y-J, Bai H-W, Wu X, Gao Y-H, Liu X-C, Wang J-C, Wang Q. Microstructure and mechanical behavior of rhombic dodecahedron-structured porous β -Ti composites fabricated via laser powder bed fusion. *J Mater Res Technol* 2024;31:298–310.
- [13] Prajapati MJ, Kumar A, Lin S-C, Jeng J-Y. Multi-material additive manufacturing with lightweight closed-cell foam-filled lattice structures for enhanced mechanical and functional properties. *Addit Manuf* 2022;54:102766.
- [14] Alammar A, Kojs JC, Revilla-León M, Att W. Additive manufacturing technologies: current status and future perspectives. *J Prosthodont* 2022;31(S1):4–12.
- [15] C. Cai, K. Zhou, Chapter 7 - metal additive manufacturing, in: C.D. Patel, C.-H. Chen (Eds.), *Digital manufacturing*, Elsevier2022, pp. 247-298.

- [16] Wang J, Zhu R, Liu Y, Zhang L. Understanding melt pool characteristics in laser powder bed fusion: an overview of single- and multi-track melt pools for process optimization. *Advan Pow Mater* 2023;2(4):100137.
- [17] Svetlizky D, Das M, Zheng B, Vyatskikh AL, Bose S, Bandyopadhyay A, Schoenung JM, Lavernia EJ, Eliaz N. Directed energy deposition (DED) additive manufacturing: physical characteristics, defects, challenges and applications. *Mater Today* 2021;49:271–95.
- [18] Thompson SM, Bian L, Shamsaei N, Yadollahi A. An overview of Direct Laser Deposition for additive manufacturing; Part I: transport phenomena, modeling and diagnostics. *Addit Manuf* 2015;8:36–62.
- [19] Zhang W, Yang M, Mao W, Takesue S, Soshi M. The effect of productive and quality deposition strategies on residual stress for Directed Energy Deposition (DED) process. *Manufact Lett* 2024;41:868–78.
- [20] Nguyen HD, Pramanik A, Basak AK, Dong Y, Prakash C, Debnath S, Shankar S, Jawahir IS, Dixit S, Buddhi D. A critical review on additive manufacturing of Ti-6Al-4V alloy: microstructure and mechanical properties. *J Mater Res Technol* 2022;18:4641–61.
- [21] Wang X, Lv F, Shen L, Liang H-X, Xie D-Q, Tian Z-J. Influence of island scanning strategy on microstructures and mechanical properties of direct laser-deposited Ti-6Al-4V structures. *Acta Metall Sin* 2018;32 (English Letters).
- [22] Oh H, Lee J, Kim JG, Kim S. Effect of defects on environment-assisted fracture (EAF) behavior of Ti-6Al-4V alloy fabricated by direct energy deposition (DED). *J Mater Res Technol* 2022;20:4365–77.
- [23] Kistler NA, Corbin DJ, Nassar AR, Reutzel EW, Beese AM. Effect of processing conditions on the microstructure, porosity, and mechanical properties of Ti-6Al-4V repair fabricated by directed energy deposition. *J Mater Process Technol* 2019;264:172–81.
- [24] Wu X, Liang J, Mei J, Mitchell C, Goodwin PS, Voice W. Microstructures of laser-deposited Ti-6Al-4V. *Mater Des* 2004;25:137–44.
- [25] Bai P, Chen M, Du W, Zhao Z, Wang S, Li Y. Microstructural evolution and mechanical properties of TiC/Ti6Al4V composites manufactured by selective laser melting after solution and aging treatments. *Results Phys* 2024;61:107781.
- [26] Panin A, Kazachenok M, Kolmakov A, Chizhik S, Heifetz M, Chugui Y. Microstructure and mechanical behaviour of additive manufactured Ti-6Al-4V parts under tension. *EPJ Web Conf* 2019;221:01037.
- [27] Tao P, Li H-x, Huang B-y, Hu Q-d, Gong S-l, Xu Q. Tensile behavior of Ti-6Al-4V alloy fabricated by selective laser melting: effects of microstructures and as-built surface quality. *China Found* 2018;15:243–52.
- [28] Vrancken B, Thijs L, Kruth J-P, Van Humbeeck J. Heat treatment of Ti6Al4V produced by selective laser melting: microstructure and mechanical properties. *J Alloys Compd* 2012;541:177–85.
- [29] Wang D, Wang H, Chen X, Liu Y, Lu D, Liu X, Han C. Densification, tailored microstructure, and mechanical properties of selective laser melted Ti-6Al-4V alloy via annealing heat treatment. *Micromachines* 2022;13:331.
- [30] Wang H, Chao Q, Chen HS, Chen ZB, Primig S, Xu W, Ringer SP, Liao XZ. Formation of a transition V-rich structure during the α' to $\alpha + \beta$ phase transformation process in additively manufactured Ti-6Al-4 V. *Acta Mater* 2022; 235:118104.
- [31] Wu M-W, Chen J-K, Lin B-H, Chiang P-H, Tsai M-K. Compressive fatigue properties of additive-manufactured Ti-6Al-4V cellular material with different porosities. *Mater Sci Eng, A* 2020;790:139695.
- [32] Wu SQ, Lu YJ, Gan YL, Huang TT, Zhao CQ, Lin JJ, Guo S, Lin JX. Microstructural evolution and microhardness of a selective-laser-melted Ti-6Al-4V alloy after post heat treatments. *J Alloys Compd* 2016;672:643–52.
- [33] Yang J, Yu H, Yin J, Gao M, Wang Z, Zeng X. Formation and control of martensite in Ti-6Al-4V alloy produced by selective laser melting. *Mater Des* 2016;108:308–18.
- [34] Etesami A, Fotovvati B, Asadi E. Heat treatment of Ti-6Al-4V alloy manufactured by laser-based powder-bed fusion: process, microstructures, and mechanical properties correlations. *J Alloys Compd* 2021;895:162618.
- [35] Qian L, Mei J, Liang J, Wu X. Influence of position and laser power on thermal history and microstructure of direct laser fabricated Ti-6Al-4V samples. *Mater Sci Technol* 2005;21(5):597–605.
- [36] Malej S, Godec M, Donik Č, Balazic M, Zettler R, Lienert T, Pambaguian L. Hybrid additive manufacturing of Ti6Al4V with powder-bed fusion and direct-energy deposition. *Mater Sci Eng, A* 2023;878:145229.
- [37] Roudnická M, Kacénka Z, Dvorsky D, Drahoukoupil J, Vojtech D. Hydrogen embrittlement of Ti-Al6-V4 alloy manufactured by laser powder bed fusion induced by electrochemical charging. *Metals* 2024.
- [38] Karimi P, Sadeghi E, Ålgårdh J, Keshavarzkermani A, Esmaeilizadeh R, Toyserkani E, Andersson J. Columnar-to-equiaxed grain transition in powder bed fusion via mimicking casting solidification and promoting in situ recrystallization. *Addit Manuf* 2021;46:102086.
- [39] Chen C, Liu L, Zhao R, Cao T, Hu T, Xu S, Shuai S, Yin S, Wang J, Liao H, Ren Z. Microstructure evolution and mechanical properties of laser additive manufactured Ti6Al4V alloy under nitrogen-argon reactive atmosphere. *Mater Sci Eng, A* 2022; 841:143076.
- [40] Lekoadi P, Tlotleng M, Annan K, Maledi N, Masina B. Evaluation of heat treatment parameters on microstructure and hardness properties of high-speed selective laser melted Ti6Al4V. *Metals* 2021;11(2):255.
- [41] Kassym K, Perveen A. Atomization processes of metal powders for 3D printing. *Mater Today Proc* 2020;26:1727–33.
- [42] Wysocki B, Maj P, Sitek R, Buhagiar J, Kurzydowski KJ, Świączkowski W. Laser and electron beam additive manufacturing methods of fabricating titanium bone implants. *Appl Sci* 2017;7(7):657.
- [43] Fiolek A, Zimowski S, Kopia A, Moskalewicz T. The influence of electrophoretic deposition parameters and heat treatment on the microstructure and tribological properties of nanocomposite Si3N4/PEEK 708 coatings on titanium alloy. *Coatings* 2019;9(9):530.
- [44] Zhang Z, Ge P, Li JY, Ren DX, Wu T. Monte Carlo simulations of solidification and solid-state phase transformation during directed energy deposition additive manufacturing. *Prog Add Manuf* 2022;7(4):671–82.
- [45] Sahoo S, Joshi A, Balla VK, Das M, Roy S. Site-specific microstructure, porosity and mechanical properties of LENSTM processed Ti-6Al-4V alloy. *Mater Sci Eng, A* 2021;820:141494.
- [46] Cao F, Zhang T, Ryder MA, Lados DA. A review of the fatigue properties of additively manufactured Ti-6Al-4V. *J Occup Med* 2018;70(3):349–57.
- [47] Roudnická M. Structure and properties of metal materials produced by 3D printing methods. Prague: UCT Prague; 2020.
- [48] Vojtěch D. In: Kovové materiály. 1. ed. Praha: VŠCHT; 2006.
- [49] Yu J, Rombouts M, Maes G, Motmans F. Material properties of Ti6Al4V parts produced by laser metal deposition. *Phys Procedia* 2012;39:416–24.
- [50] Carroll BE, Palmer TA, Beese AM. Anisotropic tensile behavior of Ti-6Al-4V components fabricated with directed energy deposition additive manufacturing. *Acta Mater* 2015;87:309–20.
- [51] Roudnická M, Misurak M, Vojtech D. Differences in the response of additively manufactured titanium alloy to heat treatment - comparison between SLM and EBM. *Manufact Technol J* 2019;19(4):668–73.
- [52] Ye X-C, Xiao K-Q, Cao R-X, Wu H, Zhao G-w, Li B. Microstructure evolution and microhardness of TiAl based alloy blade by vacuum suction casting. *Vacuum* 2019; 163:186–93.
- [53] Çömez N, Yurddaskal M, Durmuş H. Effect of solutionizing and quenching treatment on Ti6Al4V alloy: a study on wear, cavitation erosion and corrosion resistance. *J Mater Sci* 2023;58(24):10201–16.